

[[研究文章 Research Article]]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19327737>臺灣產虹尺蛾屬 (*Acolutha*) 幼生期短記 (鱗翅目：尺蛾科：波尺蛾亞科)吳士緯¹、羅忠良²、謝振邦³¹國立臺灣博物館 臺北市襄陽路 2 號 Email: spwu@ntm.gov.tw²臺中市新社區東興里興社街一段國校巷 13 號³嘉義東區五峰路131巷40號

摘要: 本文章確認臺灣產虹尺蛾屬 (*Acolutha*) 兩物種幼蟲皆取食杜英科植物，即虹尺蛾取食杜英與薯豆、霓虹尺蛾取食杜英。此外，亦提出臺灣產虹尺蛾屬物種過往至今的中文名稱使用建議。

關鍵詞: 東方區、東亞、杜英科、寄主植物

前言

分布於東方區的尺蛾科 (Geometridae) 波尺蛾亞科 (Larentiinae) 虹尺蛾屬 (*Acolutha* Warren, 1894) 已知共有 9 個物種，該屬的模式物種為 *A. pictaria* (Moore, 1888) (Parsons et al., 1999)。此屬臺灣分布種級物種，即 *A. pictaria* (Moore, 1888) 與 *A. pulchella* (Hampson, 1891)，前者於日本，後者於日本及香港產個體具有幼生期紀錄 (Koshino, 1998; Koshino, 1999; Tominaga, 2003; Young & Wu, 2023)。本研究確認該兩臺灣物種之族群亦取食杜英科植物葉片，並於此紀錄。此外，據 Wu 與 Li (2025) 的原則提供對臺灣分類群的中文名建議。

材料與方法

採集之幼蟲以 5*10*10 公分透明塑膠容器裝填足量寄主植物飼養至成蟲。成蟲存證標本皆存放於國立臺灣博物館，臺北 (NTM, National Taiwan Museum, Taipei) 與國立自然科學博物館，臺中 (NMNS, National Museum of Natural Science, Taichung)。

結果

Acolutha pictaria imbecilla Warren, 1905 虹尺蛾、前褐帶黃波尺蛾
(圖一 a, b)

Emmelesia pictaria Moore, 1888, *Descriptions of new Indian lepidopterous insects from the collection of the late Mr. W.S. Atkinson* (3): 267.

Acolutha imbecilla Warren, 1905, *Novitates Zoologicae* 12: 426.

標本檢視：TAIWAN: 1 male, Taichung City, Dakeng No. 5-1 trail, 24. III. 2025, leg. C. L. Luo, reared from *Elaeocarpus sylvestris* (NTM); 1 male, 2 females, ditto except collecting date: 21. IV. 2025, SWUBR2025-042, SWC2024-2130~2032 (NTM); 1 male, Nantou County, Benbu River, 24.002288, 121.052334, 14. I. 2016, leg. Z. B. Xie, reared from *Elaeocarpus japonicus*, CB613 (NTM); 1 male, Kaohsiung, Taoyuan, Tengjih, 1550 m, 22. III. 1991, leg. H. Y. Wang (NMNS).

鑑定：臺灣已知僅有與霓虹尺蛾 (*A. pulchella semifulva*)，成蟲與幼蟲外觀辨識容易。虹尺蛾成蟲 (圖一 1a) 前翅長約 8-9 公釐，霓虹尺蛾 (圖一 c) 約 10-11 公釐；前種前翅近外緣半部呈淡棕色，與其餘區段分界較不明顯，後種近外緣半部呈棕色，與其餘區段分界明顯，此外亞外緣線明顯呈黑棕色，亞外緣線與外緣間近內緣半部大體呈粉白色，近臀角具有一處大黑暈斑；前種後翅橫向具有規則的黃色、白色、淡棕色排列紋路，後種除了中線呈黃色以外，其餘為粉白底色參有灰黑色暈紋。虹尺蛾 (圖一 1b) 終齡蟲長約 15 公釐，霓虹尺蛾 (圖一 1d) 約 17 公釐；前種頭部綠色或淡橙色，後種多為橙色；兩物種體軀主要為綠色帶有反射光折，前種體側或多或少具有縱向紅色線紋，足與腹足綠色，後種體側各節具有帶狀致紡錘狀的鮮紅色斑，最後一對腹足亦呈鮮紅色。

寄主：臺灣幼蟲取食杜英科 (Elaeocarpaceae) 杜英 (*Elaeocarpus sylvestris*) 以及薯豆 (*E. japonicus*)，已知至少取食杜英的幼蟲偏好成葉。日本族群視為亞種 *shirozui*，幼蟲首次記錄於沖繩，亦取食杜英 (Tominaga, 2003)。

中文名：虹尺蛾屬模式種 *A. pictaria* 過往於臺灣出版品使用之對應中文名包含前褐帶黃波尺蛾 (Chang, 1990; Fu et al., 1995; Wang, 1997; Hsu & Hsu, 2017) 以及虹尺蛾 (Fu & Tzuoo, 2002; Yao & Luo, 2011; Chen, 2011; Fu et al., 2020)，然此些出版品僅提供種級中文名，並未提供屬級之中文名。本文章參考 Xue 與 Zhu 的研究 (1999)，建議屬級與種級分別以「虹尺蛾屬」與「虹尺蛾」稱之。

Acolutha pulchella semifulva Warren, 1905 霓虹尺蛾、前褐帶波尺蛾
(圖一 c, d)

Hyria pulchella Hampson, 1891, *Illustr. typical Specimens Lepid. Heterocera Colin Br. Mus.* 8: 32, 124, pl. 153, fig. 22.

Acolutha semifulva Warren, 1905, *Novitates Zoologicae* 12: 426.

標本檢視：TAIWAN: 3 females, Taichung City, Xinshe, Shanghengping, 29. III. 2025, leg. C. L. Luo, SWC2024-2088~2090; 1 female, Nantou Co., Nengkao Waterfall, 643 m, 24.025833, 120.977472, 9. XI. 2015, leg. Z. B. Xie, CB583.

鑑定：見前種。

寄主：臺灣幼蟲取食杜英科 (Elaeocarpaceae) 杜英 (*Elaeocarpus sylvestris*)，幼蟲能取食幼葉與成葉。日本同亞種幼蟲寄主包含薯豆 (Koshino, 1998; Koshino, 1999; Tominaga, 2003)，其中，Tominaga (2003) 修正早先文獻，即 Tominaga (2000) 所記載的虎皮楠科 (Daphniphyllaceae) 食草 *D. glaucescens* var. *teijsmannii* 為薯豆。香港同種級 (*A. pulchella*) 幼蟲取食杜英與顯脈杜英 (*E. dubius*) (Young & Wu, 2023)。

中文名：據前種之考量，本種 (*A. pulchella*) 之中文名建議參考 Xue 與 Zhu (1999) 使用霓虹尺蛾，此外過往使用中文名包含前褐帶波尺蛾 (Fu et al., 1995; Wang, 1997; Hsu & Hsu, 2017)。

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引用文獻

- Chang, B. S. 1990. Illustrations of Moths in Taiwan. Vol. 3. Taipei: Taiwan Museum. 355 pp. (in Chinese)
- Chen, M. Y. 2011. Facing moths in the stary night- handbook for moth observation in Mei-Feng. Nantou: Meifeng Farm. 239 pp. (in Chinese)
- Fu, C. M. & Tzuoo, H. R. 2002. Moths of Anmashan, Part 1. Taichung Nature Research Society, Taichung. 127 pp + pls 1–36.
- Fu, C. M., Tzuoo, H. R. & Chen, W. H. 1995. Survey of the Moths at Pahsienshan Area. Self-published, Taipei. 88 pp.
- Fu, C.-M., Wu, S. & Shih, L.-C. 2020. Geometridae, Larentiinae. In: Fu, C.-M., Owada, M., Shih, L.-C. & Lin, H.-H. (eds), Moths of Nanheng Part 1. Endemic Species Research Institute, Nantou. pp. 248–339.
- Hampson, G. F. 1891. The Lepidoptera Heterocera of the Nilgiri district. Illustrations of typical specimens of Lepidoptera Heterocera in the collection of the British Museum. Part VIII. The Lepidoptera Heterocera of the Nilgiri district. Part 8: 1–iv, 1–144, pls. 139–156.
- Hsu, Y. F & Hsu, Y. M. 2017. Moths of Yangmingshan National Park. Taipei: Yangmingshan National Park. 319 pp.
- Koshino, S. 1998. Larva of *Acolutha pulchella* (Hampson) (Geometridae, Larentiinae) feeding on *Elaeocarpus sylvestris* (Elaeocarpaceae). *Japan Heterocerists' Journal* 198: 394. (in Japanese)
- Koshino, S. 1999. Further notes and illustration of larva of *Acolutha pulchella* (Hampson) (Geometridae, Larentiinae) on *Elaeocarpus* (Elaeocarpaceae). *Japan Heterocerists' Journal* 205: 81–82. (in Japanese)
- Moore, F. 1888. Descriptions of New Indian Lepidopterous Insects from the collection of the late Mr. W. S. Atkinson – Heterocera. Part 3. Taylor & Francis, London 199–299.
- Parsons, M. S., Scoble, M. J., Honey, M. R., Pitkin, L. M. & Pitkin, B. R. 1999. The catalogue. In: Scoble, M. J. (ed.), Geometrid Moths of the World: A Catalogue (Lepidoptera, Geometridae). Vol. 1 & 2. CSIRO Publishing, Collingwood & Stenstrup, 1016 pp.

- Tominaga, S. 2000. Host plants of two species of Larentiinae (Geometridae) in Okinawa Island. *Gekkan-Mushi* 358: 45. (in Japanese)
- Tominaga, S. 2003. Biological notes on seven species of the Geometridae in Okinawa Island. *Yugato* 173: 105–109. (in Japanese)
- Wang, H. Y. 1997. Geometer Moths of Taiwan and It's allied Species from the neighboring countries Vol. 1. Taipei: Taiwan Museum. 405 pp. (in Chinese)
- Warren, W. 1905. New species of Thyrididae, Uraniidae, and Geometridae, from the Oriental Region. *Novitates Zoologicae* 12: 410–491.
- Wu, S. & Li, H.-H. 2025. On the insect Chinese vernacular name promotion in Taiwan - review and prospects. *Journal of National Taiwan Museum* 78 (1): 27–47.
- Xue, D. Y. & Zhu, H. F. 1999. Fauna Sinica. Insecta Vol. 15, Lepidoptera, Geometridae, Larentiinae. Beijing: Science Press. 1090 pp, pls. 25. (in Chinese)
- Yao, C. T & Luo, Y. J. 2011. Moths of the Tengjih National Forest Recreation Area. Pingtung Forest District Office, Pingtung. 131 pp.
- Young, J. J. & Wu, J. C. S. 2023. A Monograph on the Life Histories of Moths from Hong Kong & Neighbouring Areas (Vol. 2). Hong Kong Lepidopterists' Society, Hong Kong. 380 pp.

A Short Note on the Immature Stages of *Acolutha* Warren, 1894 in Taiwan (Lepidoptera, Geometridae, Larentiinae)

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Abstract: This study confirms that the larvae of two *Acolutha* species occurring in Taiwan both feed on plants of the family Elaeocarpaceae: *A. pictaria imbecilla* Warren, 1905 feeds on *E. sylvestris* and *E. japonicus*, while *A. pulchella semifulva* Warren, 1905 feeds on *E. sylvestris*. In addition, suggestions are provided regarding the usage of Chinese vernacular names for Taiwanese *Acolutha* species, based on historical and current practices.

Keywords: Oriental region, East Asia, Elaeocarpaceae, hostplant

圖一. 臺灣產虹尺蛾屬 (*Acolutha* Warren, 1894) 物種。a. 虹尺蛾 (*A. pictaria imbecilla* Warren, 1905) 雄成蟲標本；b. 同上，終齡幼蟲；c. 霓虹尺蛾 (*A. pulchella semifulva* Warren, 1905) 雌成蟲標本；d. 同上，終齡幼蟲。攝影：吳士緯 (a, c)；羅忠良 (b, d)。